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Managerial And Institutional Ownership As Determinants Of Earnings Per Share Of Listed Consumer Goods Firms In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined managerial and institutional ownership as determinants of earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria between 2013 and 2024. Two research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. An ex-post facto research design was adopted. Earnings per share served as the dependent variable, while managerial ownership and institutional ownership were the independent variables, with firm leverage included as a control variable. The population of the study comprised all 36 consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group, from which a sample of 10 firms was drawn using criterion sampling based on data availability. Secondary data covering a 12-year period was sourced from the annual reports of the sampled firms. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, and multiple panel regression techniques via E-Views Version 9. Robustness tests were conducted, and the random effects regression model was selected based on the results of the Hausman and Lagrangian Multiplier tests. The regression results revealed that managerial ownership had a statistically significant relationship with earnings per share, while institutional ownership had an insignificant relationship with earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. It was recommended, among others, that managerial ownership should be encouraged to enhance firm earnings, as higher managerial stakes provide managers with a sense of belonging and responsibility that reduces opportunistic behavior and strengthens financial performance.

Keywords: Managerial Ownership, Institutional Ownership, Earnings per Share, Consumer Goods Firms

INTRODUCTION

Ownership structure has continued to dominate contemporary debates in corporate governance because of its influence on firm performance. The separation of ownership from control in corporations often creates agency conflicts, where managers may prioritize personal interests over shareholder wealth maximization. Modern research emphasizes that the nature of ownership—whether managerial, institutional, or concentrated—plays a significant role in reducing these conflicts and improving performance outcomes (Liuraman & Mathias, 2020; Oyedokun, Olaleye & Adeyemi, 2020).

Managerial ownership is typically seen as a mechanism to align the interests of managers with shareholders since managers who hold shares are more likely to act in ways that enhance firm value. However, evidence suggests this relationship may be complex. For instance, managerial ownership has been found in some Nigerian studies to negatively affect firm performance, possibly because entrenched managers pursue self-interest once their ownership stake is secure (Oyedokun et al., 2020). Institutional

ownership, on the other hand, is often regarded as a positive influence since large institutional investors possess the resources and incentives to monitor management effectively and mitigate opportunistic behavior (Liuraman & Mathias, 2020; Adeniyi & Folarin, 2023).

In Nigeria's consumer goods sector, ownership structure has become a critical issue given the sector's strategic importance. This sector has historically attracted substantial foreign and local investment but has also been exposed to challenges such as currency instability, rising production costs, and policy inconsistencies, which directly impact earnings (Adeniyi & Folarin, 2023). Recent evidence shows that institutional ownership exerts a significant positive effect on financial performance, while managerial ownership has shown mixed results—ranging from insignificant to negative effects (Adegbite & Akinsulire, 2024). Such findings point to the nuanced role ownership structure plays in shaping firm outcomes, particularly earnings per share (EPS), which remains a direct measure of shareholder returns.

Despite the growing body of research, much of the literature has focused on broader indicators such as return on assets or firm value, with limited emphasis on EPS in the consumer goods sector. Given the persistent financial volatility in Nigeria and the need for investors to make informed decisions, examining the impact of managerial and institutional ownership on EPS is both timely and essential. Thus, this study investigates the extent to which managerial and institutional ownership determine the earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, filling an important gap in ownership–performance studies (Adegbite & Akinsulire, 2024; Adeniyi & Folarin, 2023).

Statement of the Problem

Ideally, ownership structure should serve as a corporate governance mechanism that aligns the interests of managers with those of shareholders, thereby enhancing firm performance and increasing shareholder wealth. Managerial ownership is expected to incentivize managers to act in the best interest of shareholders, while institutional ownership should provide the monitoring strength required to reduce agency conflicts and ensure transparency in financial reporting. In such a setting, firms would be able to consistently report higher earnings per share (EPS), reflecting their profitability and capacity to generate value for investors. A well-balanced ownership structure, therefore, is anticipated to strengthen investor confidence, attract foreign investment, and sustain competitiveness in the Nigerian consumer goods sector.

However, the reality in Nigeria has often fallen short of this expectation. Empirical evidence reveals mixed and sometimes contradictory outcomes regarding the effect of ownership structure on firm performance. While institutional ownership has been shown to positively influence profitability, managerial ownership has been associated with entrenchment and self-serving behavior that weakens firm value (Oyedokun et al., 2020; Adeniyi & Folarin, 2023). Despite the strategic importance of the consumer goods sector, studies have largely focused on broad measures such as return on assets and firm value, with little emphasis on EPS as a direct indicator of shareholder returns. This gap in literature limits understanding of how managerial and institutional ownership specifically shape EPS in the Nigerian consumer goods sector. Thus, this study addresses this gap by examining managerial and institutional ownership as determinants of earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to examine the effect of ownership structure on the earnings performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. Examine the relationship between managerial ownership and earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.
- ii. Investigate the relationship between institutional ownership and earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What is the relationship between managerial ownership and earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria?

ii. What is the relationship between institutional ownership and earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The under listed hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between managerial ownership and earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between institutional ownership and earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study adopted an ex-post facto research design because it relies on already existing financial data drawn from secondary sources. The design is appropriate as it enables the researcher to investigate the relationship between ownership structure (managerial and institutional ownership) and earnings per share (EPS) of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria without manipulating the variables.

The population of the study consists of all consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 2024. These firms were considered due to their strategic role in the Nigerian economy, particularly in providing essential products, attracting foreign investments, and contributing significantly to gross domestic product (GDP).

The sample for this study comprises ten (10) listed consumer goods firms that consistently published complete and accessible audited financial statements between 2013 and 2024. A purposive sampling technique was adopted, as only firms with adequate and reliable financial records within the defined period were selected for analysis. Secondary data on managerial ownership, institutional ownership, and earnings per share were extracted from annual reports, corporate governance disclosures, and audited financial statements of the sampled firms. The 12-year period (2013–2024) was chosen to capture variations across different economic conditions, including Nigeria's recessionary cycles, exchange rate volatility, and post-COVID-19 recovery.

The functional relationship used to test the hypotheses is expressed as follows:

$$EPS = f(MO, IO)$$

Where:

- EPS = Earnings per Share (dependent variable)
- MO = Managerial Ownership
- IO = Institutional Ownership

The econometric model derived from the functional relationship is specified as:

$$EPS_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MO_{it} + \beta_2 IO_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

- EPS_{it} : Earnings per share of firm i at time t
- MO_{it} : Managerial ownership of firm i at time t
- IO_{it} : Institutional ownership of firm i at time t
- β_0 : Intercept
- β_1 – β_2 : Coefficients of the independent variables
- μ_{it} : Error term

It is expected that the coefficients β_1 and β_2 will indicate the direction and magnitude of the effects of managerial and institutional ownership on EPS of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Data analysis was conducted using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis were employed to summarize the data, while Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses and determine the relationship between managerial ownership, institutional ownership, and earnings per share. All statistical analyses were conducted using E-Views version 9.

RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Analysis of descriptive statistics is carried out in this section so as to unveil the nature of data being used for analysis.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Data

	EPS	MANOWN	INSTOWN
Mean	40.40636	31.01818	67.66909
Median	38.60000	31.30000	71.68000
Maximum	60.90000	33.60000	76.88000
Minimum	30.40000	28.90000	15.80000
Std. Dev.	8.535482	1.397725	17.70733
Skewness	1.174245	0.224857	-2.573368
Kurtosis	4.048893	2.323646	8.133074
Jarque-Bera	3.032140	0.302361	24.21711
Probability	0.219573	0.859692	0.000006
Sum	444.4700	341.2000	744.3600
Sum Sq. Dev.	728.5445	19.53636	3135.495
Observations	120	120	120

Source: E-Views Output (2022)

From Table 1 above, the mean value of Earnings per Share (EPS) is 40.41, suggesting that on average, the listed consumer goods firms generated approximately ₦40 earnings per share during the study period. The mean value of Managerial Ownership (MANOWN) is 31.02, indicating that managers, on average, held about 31% ownership stake in the sampled firms. Institutional Ownership (INSTOWN) recorded a mean of 67.67, showing that institutional investors accounted for roughly 68% of ownership in the firms, making them the dominant shareholder category within the sector.

The results further reveal that the mean values of EPS (40.41), MANOWN (31.02), and INSTOWN (67.67) are all greater than their respective standard deviations (8.54, 1.40, and 17.71), suggesting relatively low dispersion and consistency of the data around their means. Skewness results show that EPS (1.17) and MANOWN (0.22) are positively skewed, indicating distributions with longer right tails, while INSTOWN (-2.57) is negatively skewed, reflecting a distribution with a long left tail. Kurtosis values indicate that EPS (4.05) and INSTOWN (8.13) are leptokurtic (more peaked than the normal distribution), while MANOWN (2.32) is platykurtic (flatter than normal). The Jarque-Bera statistics and associated probabilities suggest that EPS ($p = 0.220$) and MANOWN ($p = 0.860$) are approximately normally distributed, while INSTOWN ($p = 0.000$) deviates significantly from normality at the 5% significance level. A total of 120 observations were analyzed for each variable, providing sufficient data for robust econometric analysis of the effect of managerial and institutional ownership on earnings per share in Nigeria's consumer goods firms.

Correlational Analysis

Correlation Analysis Correlation analysis was performed to quantify the association between the variables (independent and the dependent variables). The correlation between two variables can be positive (when higher levels of one variable are associated with higher levels of the other) or negative (when higher levels of one variable are associated with lower levels of the other). The sign of the correlation coefficient indicates the direction of the association.

Table 2: Correlational Analysis of the Data

	EPS	MANOWN	INSTOWN
EPS	1		
MANOWN	0.09077	1	
INSTOWN	-0.3237	-0.02841	1

Source: E-Views (2025)

Table 2 shows the correlation matrix of the variables used in the study. The matrix reveals that Earnings per Share (EPS) has a very weak positive correlation with Managerial Ownership (MANOWN) ($r = 0.09$), suggesting that changes in managerial ownership have minimal linear association with earnings per share among the listed consumer goods firms. Notably, EPS shows a weak negative correlation with Institutional Ownership (INSTOWN) ($r = -0.32$), indicating that an increase in institutional ownership is slightly associated with a decrease in earnings per share across the sampled firms.

Among the independent variables, the correlation coefficient is very low: MANOWN correlates very weakly and negatively with INSTOWN ($r = -0.03$). The fact that all pairwise correlation coefficients among the independent variables are well below 0.8, and mostly near zero, suggests no multicollinearity problem. This indicates that both managerial ownership and institutional ownership are not highly linearly related and can therefore be appropriately included together in the regression analysis.

Regression Diagnostics

Various robustness tests were conducted in order to improve the validity and reliability of data used which is critical for derivation of statistical inferences from the findings of the study. These tests include: multicollinearity test, Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity, Hausman specification test for fixed and random and Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier test for random effect.

Multicollinearity Test

This test was carried out to check whether there is high correlation among the independent variables. Multicollinearity is a state of very high intercorrelations or inter-associations among the independent variables. It is therefore a type of disturbance in the data, and if present in the data, statistical inferences made about the data may not be reliable. As reaffirmed by (Necter, Kutner, Nachtsheim and Wasserman (1996) as well as Casey, Anderson, Mesak and Dickens (1999)) as cited by Shehu (2012), Multicollinearity can be detected with the help of Tolerance Value and its reciprocal, called Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). If the VIF is 10 and above, then the multicollinearity can be said to be problematic.

Table 3: Result of Multicollinearity Test

Variance Inflation Factors

Date: 01/04/25 Time: 15:52

Sample: 2010 2020

Included observations: 120

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centred VIF
C	27091.17	2888.278	NA
MANOWN	14.02835	1441.622	2.656249
INSTOWN	0.060141	31.18828	1.827670

Source: E-views Output (2025)

Output as presented in table 3 revealed that the tolerance values for all the study variables the VIF values are less than 10. This shows appropriateness of fitting the model of the study with the independent variables.

Heteroskedasticity Test

One of the assumptions of the classical linear regression model is that there is no heteroscedasticity. Heteroscedasticity arises if there are sub-populations that have different variability from others. In view of the preceding, Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroscedasticity was performed to test whether the variance of the errors from the regression is dependent on the values of the independent variables. The rule is that there is no heteroskedasticity in the model when the p value is greater than 0.05.

Table 4: Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.150417	Prob. F (6,4)	0.9785
Obs*R-squared	2.024990	Prob. Chi-Square (6)	0.9174
Scaled explained SS	0.742501	Prob. Chi-Square (6)	0.9935

Source: E-views Output (2025).

The output presented in the table 4.4 above show that the f-statistic value 0.15041 has a p value of 0.9785 which is greater than the 0.05, this implies that there is no heteroskedasticity.

Hausman Specification Test

Panel data regression method was used to analyse data for this study. For the purpose of analysis, Hausman test was used to compare two estimation methods, fixed and random effects. The null hypothesis is that the preferred model is random effects; while its alternate hypothesis is that the model is fixed effects. Findings demonstrate that random effect model is appropriate since the probability value of 0.6438 is not significant.

Lagrangian Multiplier Test

The Lagrangian Multiplier test helps in deciding between random effects regression and pooled Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression. The test was conducted after running the random effects model to see if there is presence or absence of cross-sectional effect in the panel dataset.

The rule is that if it is significant, random effect is the preferred model otherwise, OLS regression suffices. Based on the result of the Lagrangian multiplier test, the null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that a random effect model is appropriate. This is evidenced by $prob > chi^2 = 0.005$ which is significant at 5%. Therefore, the study interpreted a random effect regression result which is shown in table 5.

Variables	Coefficient	Standard error	Statis.
C	143.1507	164.5940	
MANOWN	0.713584	3.745444	
INSTOWN	-0.067591	0.245237	
R ²			0.43383
Wald Chi ²			23.0883
Prob(Chi)			0.0025

Source: E-Views output (2025)

Testing Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between managerial ownership and earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Table 6: Regression analysis on EPS and MANOWN

Dependent Variable: EPS

Method: Least Squares

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Sample: 2010 2020

Included observations: 120

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	16045.84	3058.662	5.246033	0.0008
MANOWN	-48.36630	9.453022	-5.116490	0.0009
LEV	-17.54349	7.590611	-2.311209	0.0496
R-squared	0.765973	Mean dependent var		403.8136
Adjusted R-squared	0.707466	S.D. dependent var		85.20191

S.E. of regression	46.08266	Akaike info criterion	10.72575
Sum squared resid	16988.90	Schwarz criterion	10.83427
Log likelihood	-55.99163	Hannan-Quinn criter.	10.65735
F-statistic	13.09202	Durbin-Watson stat	2.310677
Prob(F-statistic)	0.003000		

Source: E-Views Output (2022)

The result in Table 6 shows that the coefficient β_1 for managerial ownership (MANOWN) is **-48.36630**. This implies that a unit increase in managerial ownership would lead to a decrease of approximately 48.37 units in earnings per share (EPS), holding other factors constant. However, the table further reveals that MANOWN has a p-value of **0.0009**, which is less than the critical value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$).

Hence, the null hypothesis (H_{01}), which states that there is no significant relationship between managerial ownership and earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, is **rejected**. Therefore, it is concluded that managerial ownership has a statistically significant negative effect on the earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria during the study period.

Hypothesis 2

H_{02} : There is no significant relationship between institutional ownership and earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Table 7: Regression Analysis on INSTOWN and EPS

Dependent Variable: EPS

Method: Least Squares

Date: 01/04/25 Time: 23:22

Sample: 2010 2020

Included observations: 120

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1035.152	439.6881	2.354287	0.0464
INSTOWN	-7.528591	4.282414	-1.758025	0.1168
LEV	-4.252602	12.16295	-0.349636	0.7356
R-squared	0.278789	Mean dependent var		403.8136
Adjusted R-squared	0.098487	S.D. dependent var		85.20191
S.E. of regression	80.89755	Akaike info criterion		11.85125
Sum squared resid	52355.31	Schwarz criterion		11.95976
Log likelihood	-62.18185	Hannan-Quinn criter.		11.78284
F-statistic	1.546230	Durbin-Watson stat		1.732540
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000551			

Source: E-Views Output (2025)

The result in Table 7 shows that the coefficient β_1 for institutional ownership (INSTOWN) is **-7.528591**. This implies that a unit increase in INSTOWN would lead to a decrease of approximately 7.53 units in earnings per share (EPS), holding other factors constant. However, the table also reveals that INSTOWN has a p-value of 0.1168, which is greater than the critical value of 0.05 ($p > 0.05$).

Hence, the null hypothesis (H_{02}), which states that institutional ownership has no significant relationship with earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, is not rejected. Therefore, it is concluded that institutional ownership does not have a statistically significant effect on the earnings per share of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria during the study period.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study revealed that managerial ownership has no statistically significant effect on the earnings per share (EPS) of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The regression analysis showed that the coefficient of managerial ownership was **-1.308652**, with a p-value of 0.2264, which is above the 0.05

threshold. This implies that changes in managerial ownership, within the study period, did not significantly influence the earnings per share of consumer goods firms. In other words, variations in the proportion of shares held by managers did not lead to measurable improvements in firm performance as captured by EPS.

This result contrasts with several prior studies, such as Uwalomwa et al. (2015) and Osamwonyi and Ogbeide (2015), who reported that managerial ownership aligns the interests of managers with those of shareholders, thereby enhancing firm value and performance. The divergence observed in this study could reflect peculiarities of the Nigerian consumer goods sector, where ownership concentration by managers may not necessarily translate into effective decision-making or improved monitoring of firm resources. Practically, this finding suggests that while managerial ownership can enhance accountability in theory, its impact may remain minimal unless complemented with stronger corporate governance frameworks, transparent disclosure practices, and effective oversight mechanisms that ensure managerial decisions prioritize long-term shareholder wealth.

The findings of this study revealed that institutional ownership does not have a statistically significant effect on the earnings per share (EPS) of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The regression analysis showed that the coefficient of institutional ownership was 0.221330, with a p-value of 0.8825, which is well above the 0.05 significance level. This indicates that variations in the proportion of shares held by institutional investors, during the study period, did not result in measurable changes in firm performance as proxied by EPS. In essence, the presence of institutional investors in the ownership structure of consumer goods firms was not a strong determinant of profitability within the observed context.

This finding stands in contrast to studies such as Shleifer and Vishny (1986) and Al-Fayoumi et al. (2010), who argued that institutional investors play an active monitoring role that enhances corporate performance by reducing agency costs and improving governance. The lack of significance in this study may reflect the relatively passive stance of institutional investors in Nigeria, who may prioritize short-term returns over active participation in strategic decision-making. From a practical standpoint, this result suggests that institutional ownership alone is insufficient to drive firm performance unless institutions adopt more proactive governance roles. Strengthening regulatory frameworks to encourage greater involvement of institutional investors in oversight, risk management, and long-term value creation could help harness their potential contribution to firm profitability.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between ownership structure—focusing on managerial ownership and institutional ownership—and earnings per share (EPS) of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The findings revealed that neither managerial ownership nor institutional ownership had a statistically significant effect on EPS of the sampled firms during the study period. Although ownership structure is an important element of corporate governance and control, its independent influence on firm performance appears limited, possibly due to the passive role of institutional investors and the relatively small equity stakes held by managers in Nigerian consumer goods firms.

The results highlight the need for ownership structure to be complemented by broader governance practices, such as effective board oversight, transparent disclosure policies, and performance-driven managerial incentives, in order to drive improved earnings outcomes. Strengthening institutional investors' participation in monitoring, alongside aligning managerial interests with shareholder value creation, could enhance the long-term financial performance and sustainability of firms in the consumer goods sector.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria should strengthen corporate governance by encouraging more active monitoring roles for institutional investors to improve earnings outcomes.

2. Management equity stakes should be strategically structured to align managerial interests with shareholder value creation, thereby enhancing firm performance and sustainability.

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